

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MINORS' PARTICIPATION IN LABOR LEGAL RELATIONS

Reymbayev Abdulla Kurbanbayevich

PhD, Department of criminal law, process and criminology at the
Karakalpak State University,

Ubaydullaeva Fatima Nietullayevna

Bachelor's student in the field of Law Karakalpak State University

fatimaubaidullaeva724@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18958998>

Abstract: This study examines the employment of minors, the procedures and legal requirements for their employment, as well as the challenges they encounter in labor relations. The aim of this research is to raise public awareness about the rights of minors within labor legal relations and to outline the key criteria that should be considered when employing minors.

The research is based on systemic, logical, formal-legal, analytical, and synthetic methods. The study identifies several issues related to the protection of the labor rights of minors that remain insufficiently addressed in current practice. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the legal status of minors in labor relations and the specific characteristics of their employment.

By highlighting the legal opportunities and protections available to minors in the field of labor relations, this article seeks to promote greater awareness among the population and to support minors in effectively exercising their labor rights.

Keywords: emancipation, employment procedures, minors' rights, key criteria, entrepreneurship, child labor.

Introduction: At present, individuals who have not yet reached the age of majority increasingly seek to earn a living through their own labor. In this way, they are able to meet their personal needs and exercise their right to work, which has become a relevant and widespread phenomenon among young people. However, this issue was also relevant in earlier historical periods. The difference between the past and the present lies in the fact that, in earlier times, boys and girls were often forced to work from an early age, frequently in hazardous conditions that were harmful to their health.

In other words, child labor was widely распространено, depriving children of their right to education and causing harm to their physical, mental, and moral development. It should be noted that today child labor is prohibited worldwide.

In the modern world of advanced technologies, adolescents are provided with the necessary conditions for self-realization and receive both material and moral support. It is important to consistently highlight their rights and opportunities in labor relations so that they do not encounter legal or practical difficulties in the future. This study examines the specific features of labor relations involving minors and contributes to ensuring their lawful employment.

The topic of this scientific article has a positive impact not only on minors who wish to work, but also on their parents and employers.

To study this topic and achieve the stated objective, several tasks have been identified: to analyze the rights of minors, to outline the requirements for their

employment, to identify existing problems, and to determine possible ways of resolving them.

The object of this scientific article is the social relations that arise in the process of labor activity involving minors. The subject of the study includes labor legislation, guarantees of the labor rights of minors, and the mechanisms for their implementation. It should be noted that several research methods will be used in the course of this study in order to examine the topic in greater depth.

As previously mentioned, this topic remains significant and relevant and continues to be studied by professors and scholars to this day. At the international level, there are organizations that regulate labor relations and protect children's rights in this field, such as UNICEF and the International Labour Organization. These organizations cooperate with each other and have jointly produced reports aimed at reducing child labor and strengthening social protection.

It should also be noted that our country has legislative acts that ensure the labor rights of minors. First of all, it is necessary to mention that Article 413 of the Labor Code establishes the labor rights of persons under the age of eighteen. According to this provision, persons under eighteen years of age are granted the same rights as adult employees in individual labor relations. At the same time, in matters of occupational safety, working hours, leave, and other working conditions, they are provided with additional benefits established by labor legislation and other legal acts regulating labor.

In addition to the Labor Code, one of the key legislative acts is the Law **“On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child”** which guarantees children’s right to work. According to Article 20 of the Law “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child,” every child has the right to work, to freely choose a type of activity and profession, and to fair working conditions in accordance with their age, state of health, and professional training, in the manner established by law.

There are also other legal provisions regulating the working conditions of employees under the age of eighteen. Employers may be subject to criminal and administrative liability if they violate the norms established by these legal acts. In addition, there are state bodies responsible for ensuring and monitoring compliance with these norms, such as guardianship authorities and the Children’s Ombudsman.

It is important to emphasize the significant role of the research conducted by scholars and professors. Taking into account their opinions and judgments makes it possible to more fully reveal the relevance of this topic and helps to find answers to existing questions.

For example, independent researcher N. Abdurakhmanova from the Higher School of Judges under the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan prepared a scientific article entitled **“Legal Regulation of the Entrepreneurial Activity of Minors: Balancing the Protection of the Child’s Interests and Economic Freedom.”** This article is based on an analysis of the legal regulation of entrepreneurial activities involving minors in the Republic of Uzbekistan and proposes several recommendations for improving legislation in this field. In addition, the article discusses the concepts of legal capacity and legal competence, as well as their role in the entrepreneurial activities of individuals who have not yet reached the age of majority.

Legal capacity refers to a person’s ability to possess rights and obligations (such as the right to life, a name, and inheritance), and it arises from the moment of birth. Legal competence,

on the other hand, represents a person's ability to independently exercise their rights and fulfill their obligations, that is, to acquire and implement them on their own.

Legal competence generally depends on a person's mental condition and age. In most cases, it arises upon reaching the age of majority. However, there are different types of legal competence, including full, partial, limited, and incomplete competence. If a person has reached the age of sixteen and wishes to engage in entrepreneurial activity, they may be recognized as legally competent with the consent of their parents. This process is known as emancipation.

It is also worth noting that the article states that minors may engage in entrepreneurial activities, but only with certain protective measures and restrictions. The article also identifies various forms of entrepreneurship in which minors may participate, such as individual, family, digital, and online entrepreneurship, among others.

In her research "**Youth Unemployment in the Labor Market of Uzbekistan: Problems and Some Ways of Solving Them,**" M. Kh. Saidova examines the key difficulties faced by young people at the initial stage of their professional careers and formulates conclusions and proposals for overcoming them.

Among the identified problems is the discrepancy between the views and expectations of young people and the established social perceptions. According to the author, addressing this issue requires taking into account the opinions of young people, creating conditions for their professional and personal self-realization, and providing support for their initiatives.

Another problem is the lack of sufficient work experience among young people, while in most cases employers are reluctant to hire individuals without prior work experience. The article also emphasizes the important role of the state in addressing these issues and supporting youth employment.

As mentioned earlier, several research methods are applied in the article, including the formal-legal method, analysis, synthesis, and the systemic research method.

It is also worth noting that in the Republic of Uzbekistan citizens are allowed to work from the age of fifteen, which is established in Article 118 of the Labor Code. In labor relations involving minors, working time plays a particularly significant role. The maximum working time for minors aged 15–16 is 24 hours per week, while for those aged 16–18 it is 36 hours per week. In addition, the work performed must be light, must not be harmful to health, and must take place outside school hours.

For a minor who combines work with education, the employer must create all the necessary conditions to ensure that the work process does not interfere with the minor's studies. In addition, persons under the age of eighteen are granted additional privileges related to leave, the duration of working hours, working conditions, and other labor guarantees.

Furthermore, minors are prohibited from being employed on weekends or during night hours due to concerns for their safety and well-being.

In turn, the Republic of Uzbekistan has taken significant measures to regulate labor relations involving minors. In particular, it should be noted that Uzbekistan has ratified the Convention "**On the Prohibition and Immediate Action for the Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labour,**" adopted in Geneva on July 17, 1999.

The specific features of employing persons who have not reached the age of majority are determined by several important aspects. First of all, written consent from parents or legal guardians is required. They must be informed about the working conditions of their child and

the level of safety for their health, since in many cases adolescents may not fully understand that certain working conditions can lead to negative consequences.

There are also specific documents that must be taken into account when employing a minor, as established in Article 124 of the Labor Code of our country, **“Documents Required for Employment.”** According to this article, a person applying for a job must present the following documents:

- a passport or a substitute document, or an identification (ID) card; persons under the age of sixteen must present a birth certificate or an identification (ID) card;
- a paper employment record book or an extract from the electronic employment record book certified by the last place of employment, except for individuals applying for a job for the first time. Persons applying for part-time work instead of an employment record book must submit a certificate of the established form from their main place of employment;
- a military identification card or a registration certificate for persons liable for military service or conscripts;
- a diploma of higher education or secondary specialized or vocational education, a certificate granting the right to perform the given work, or another relevant document in cases where only persons with special education or professional training may be employed.

In general, the conducted analysis has shown that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a reliable system for guaranteeing the rights of minors in labor relations and ensures these opportunities by enshrining them in the country’s regulatory legal acts, giving them a special role in the life of the state. An analysis of legal and regulatory acts demonstrates that this area of law is widely developed and increasingly relevant today, particularly among young people, and it requires further reform and improvement.

The study also revealed that the state has various guardianship and protection bodies that safeguard children’s rights and represent their interests before the state.

Furthermore, during the course of the study, several problems faced by adolescents in the labor market were identified, and potential solutions were proposed based on the opinions of other scholars. The research method of synthesis demonstrated which rights are granted to minor workers and what obligations employers and parents have.

It should be noted that the study established that minors in labor relations are granted the same rights as adult employees. In addition, they enjoy additional benefits and guarantees, which cannot be restricted by the parties involved. Listing these rights and ensuring that adolescents understand them before employment is particularly important to prevent potential risks in the future. The article also enumerates the documents required before entering into labor relations, which can be found in the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The results obtained indicate that labor relations involving minors are sufficiently examined, and all aspects related to the topic of this article have been studied. In other words, the objectives of the research have been successfully achieved.

At the same time, the identified problems indicate the need to prevent the challenges faced by adolescents and to promote the realization of their rights by society as a whole, which demonstrates their global significance. Accordingly, it can be concluded that an important solution to issues in youth employment is to familiarize young men and women with their rights, opportunities, and relevant legal documents. Thus, the results obtained can contribute

to further research on issues in this field and have a particular impact on adolescents who wish to work, as they can better understand their legal opportunities provided by the state.

Conclusion. This article aims to examine the specific features of labor relations involving minors, their guaranteed rights, and the requirements for their employment, as well as the existing problems in exercising their labor rights. It is important to note that labor guarantees are properly implemented, and it is crucial that all parties are aware of their rights and obligations. Moreover, it can be concluded that the employment procedures for minors are determined by their age, state of health, and both physical and mental condition. This article can help enhance the legal awareness of minors and employers regarding labor relations.

References:

- 1.Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (1995). Adopted on December 21, 1995. Tashkent: Republic of Uzbekistan. Available at: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6257291>
- 2.Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY-139 (January 7, 2008). "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child." Adopted by the Legislative Chamber on November 23, 2007; Approved by the Senate on December 1, 2007. Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/1297318c>
- 3.Abdurakhmanova, N. (2024). Legal Regulation of the Entrepreneurial Activity of Minors: Balancing the Protection of the Child's Interests and Economic Freedom. Vestnik Molodykh Uchenykh [Herald of Young Scientists], 4, 99–106.
- 4.Saidova, M. Kh. (2019). Youth Unemployment in the Labor Market of Uzbekistan: Problems and Some Ways of Solving Them. Economics and Finance (Uzbekistan), (9), 43–47.

